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***DOWNLOAD, INSTALLATION AND STEPS TO USE A
PASSWORD SECURING TOOL AND ENCRYPTION
SOFTWARE***

CASE STUDY: KeePassX and Veracrypt

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1) ABSTRACT

This document outlines the procedure for downloading, installing, and utilizing KeePassX, a password management application that aids in password security. The objective is guiding through the installation process and familiarization with the application's features. This will enable safeguard of passwords and enhance overall security posture. By employing KeePassX, users can effectively manage their passwords, preventing unauthorized access and potential data breaches.

2) TABLE OF CONTENT

1) ABSTRACT-----	1
2) TABLE OF CONTENT -----	2
A. SECURING PASSWORD-----	2
1. DOWNLOAD AND INSTALLATION of KeePassX-----	2
2. GENERAL FEATURES-----	3
3. SETUP AND BASIC USAGE-----	3
B. ENCRYPTION SOFTWARE-----	7
1. DOWNLOAD AND INSTALLATION of Veracrypt -----	7
2. SETUP AND BASIC USE-----	8

A. SECURING PASSWORD

1. DOWNLOAD AND INSTALLATION of KeePassX

The download of KeePassX is done by selecting the appropriate installer file (ZIP file) for your operating system from the KeePassX official website (<https://www.keepassx.org/index.html%3Fp=21.html>)

After downloading the installer file, extract the file and run the application file. This will open the app's home page

2. GENERAL FEATURES

KeePassX is a multiplatform, open-source password manager. It is desktop-based and can however be used along with an on-line storage system, such as Dropbox.

It comes with various features, including the ability to import and export passwords, search functionality, organize passwords/user names within predefined categories and a securely generate passwords. It also comes with a limited AutoType feature, or the ability to enter user name and/or password information automatically on a Web page from an entry.

Password information is stored in an encrypted 256-bit database file.

3. SETUP AND BASIC USAGE

Upon initial launch:

- Create a new database: Click on “Database” then “New Database”. As shown in Figure 1, the Change Master Key box will be displayed, asking to create a master password for the database.

Figure 1 : The Set Master Key Box

- After creating the database, the default main window (Figure 2) appears, displaying most of KeePassX features. The menus consist of Database (New database, Open database, Recent database so on); Entries (add entry, delete entry, clone entry, copying entry information to the clipboard and others); Groups (add group, edit group, delete group); View (show toolbar); Tools (lock database, settings); and Help (About).

Figure 2: The Main KeePassX Window

- By default, database (Root) is created in the left-hand pane. To create a new group of passwords in the database, choose “Groups” then “Add New Group”, then enter the name of the new group in the Group window that appears. You also can choose an icon for the new group from the pop-up menu. After finishing, select OK. The new group will appear in the left-hand pane.
- To enter a new password and/or user name into KeePassX, select a group from the left-hand pane for the new password, then select “Entries” → “Add New Entry” or choose Add New Entry from the toolbar. A New Entry window appears (Figure 3), allowing you to enter password and user name information, along with any other needed information. Additional information you can enter includes Title (a name for the entry); Username; Password; Repeat (enter the same password twice for verification); URL (to enter the URL for which the password will give access) Notes (to enter comments about the entry); Expires (set an optional expiration date for the password).

Figure 3 :The New Entry Window for Entering New User Names and Passwords

- The password generator is available by clicking the Gen button within the New Entry window. An extension area as shown in Figure 4 appears. This feature allows you to create a random, strong password. New fields increase within which: Password (the generated password); Length (for modification of the length of the password); Character Type (select the characters to be included in the password. Lowercases, Uppercases, digits, special characters); Exclude look-alike characters; Ensure that the password contains characters from every group. Finally, the accept button to accept the generated password.
- After the password is generated, click on the “OK” button and the main window will appear as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: KeePassX Password Generator

Figure 5: Main page with Entry added

- To use a stored user name or password, copy the information from KeePassX and paste it into the required entry areas. To copy the information, select either Copy Username to Clipboard or Copy Password to Clipboard from the toolbar, or choose the same-named options under the Entries menu.
- To lock KeePassX from others' use (such as when you step away from the computer), select LockDatabase from the toolbar. To unlock KeePassX, select the Unlock button displayed, and enter the database's master password.

B. ENCRYPTION SOFTWARE

1. DOWNLOAD AND INSTALLATION of Veracrypt

The download of Veracrypt is done by selecting the appropriate installer file (ZIP file) for your operating system from the Veracrypt official website([VeraCrypt - Free Open source disk encryption with strong security for the Paranoid](#))

After downloading the installer file, extract the file and run the setup file. This will open the window shown on figure 6 to choose a language. Then a window will popup to accept the terms and conditions as shown on figure 7. After accepting the terms and conditions, you'll be prompted next to select install and click NEXT as shown on figure 8. After choosing install, you're prompted to choose the location where the software is to be installed as shown on figure 9 and click on OK.

After clicking on OK, the installation process will be launches and completed.

Figure 6 :Select language window

Figure 7: Accept license terms window

Figure 8: Install popup window

Figure 9: Window to choose installation location

2. SETUP AND BASIC USE

Upon initial launch:

- Create a Veracrypt Volume: Click on “Create Volume” button to create a new volume as shown in figure 10.
- Click on the ‘Select File’ button to: Select the file to be encrypted and click in “Create Volume”.
- Select the volume criteria to be created as shown on figure 11. In this case, the “Create and Encrypted file container” option is taken.
- Choose the volume type as shown on figure 12. In this case, the “Standard VeraCrypt volume” option is chosen.
- Choose the volume location as shown on figure 13. The location where we wish the container to be created.
- Choose the encryption option, the hashing algorithm you wish to implement as shown on figure 14.
- Specify the maximum size of the file container. As shown on figure 15. In this case, 500-megabytes container is created.
- Enter a strong password on the window represented in Figure 16
- The “Volume Format” menu will for information about the chosen format of your current virtual drive as shown in Figure 17. In this case;
 - Select the FAT option
 - Select the dynamic checkbox.
 - The “Cluster” drop-down menu is left as default.
 - Click FORMAT
- The encryption is done on the chosen file and is successful from figure 18
- To access an existing encrypted file, select the drive from the list in Figure 10, locate the file using “Select File” button and click on “Mount” button. Then enter the access password and finally, confirm that the file container has been mounted in Windows Explorer.

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18